

CHILDREN OF DIFFERENT AGES TO ORGANIZE AND CONDUCT SPORTS COMPETITIONS FOR IMPORTANCE

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Abstract. *the content of the article describes how to select young athletes and show them the right direction. Information is given that climatic-geographical, social and biological factors are important for athletes to achieve good results and achieve great goals.*

Effective organization of educational activities, i.e., sports trainings, in sports schools has been established. In order to organize physical education and sports in general schools in the same way, there should be a strong relationship between the physical education teacher or coaches conducting sports training and the students of general education schools and the parents of the participants. we can only organize effectively. These contacts are carried out through individual dialogues between teachers and students, parent meetings, and cooperative pedagogical councils of coaches and physical education teachers. This allows for the selection and orientation of children and teenagers for sports training, taking into account all the characteristics of the participants. During the selection process, as a result of conversations with parents and students, the teacher-coach gets information about normal physiological and pathological conditions of the students as well as some physical conditions. In addition, our specialists should pay attention to the factors affecting the physical development of young students during the selection process.

These are:

Biological factors; - this group is formed by genetic factors. For example, it is possible to make an approximate conclusion about the length of the future child's hair based on the height of the parents. As a result of these factors, the physical development of a person obeys the laws of nature, that is, the human body gradually changes to its youthful characteristics.

The group of climatic-geographical factors consists of climatic and meteorological factors specific to one or another region of the country. For example: In the north, the daylight hours are very short and it is very cold, while in the remote regions of Central Asia, the temperature can be very high and the humidity can be very low.

The group of social factors includes material living conditions, labor and educational activities, the content of education, including physical education. The movement of all social factors depends on the social and economic development of the country. In addition, social factors significantly affect the movement of biological and climatic-geographical factors. For example: improvement of material lifestyle has a positive effect on growth of height and development of the body, specially selected physical exercises help to overcome deficits in speed, strength and endurance caused by adverse climatic conditions.

In addition, the interests of the students, the abilities of the children in the type of sport being directed, and atropometric (body structure) characteristics are also important factors.

In general, the goal of the physical education system of Uzbekistan is to form harmoniously developed young people with spiritual wealth, moral purity, spiritual maturity and physical maturity, ready for many years of creative work and protection of the Motherland.

The main content of work in general secondary education schools and sports schools should be based on the "Alpomish" and "Barchinoy" special tests, and the physical development of young people should be planned according to their age characteristics. This is one of the most important

tasks of physical education and sports activities conducted in general secondary schools and sports schools, physical education of the young generation.

The complex of special tests "Alpomish" and "Barchinoy" consists of three stages: covers the population from 6 to 60 years of age and engages them in regular physical education and sports activities, thereby improving the health and physical fitness of the country's population. appears as the most effective means of education.

"Alpomish" and "Barchinoy" special tests are a means of promoting a healthy lifestyle, attracting the population to special training in physical education and sports, meeting the need for strengthening their health, and increasing their physical fitness at various stages of their lives. is counted. Also, the tests help to acquire the basic knowledge and practical skills of independent physical exercise, to use various forms of physical exercise in the daily routine of studying, working and relaxing, to develop mass sports in order to identify and educate talented athletes. will help.

It is necessary to note the important role of the competition in the process of training athletes of different ages. For this purpose, there is a methodical instruction entitled "Standards of competition loads and conditions of competition in sports for children and youth athletes". This instruction provides recommendations for the use of physical education and sports organizations and agencies, sports schools, and sports competitions.

Sports competitions are an important component of the educational process, and competitions have the following effects on the education of young people:

instilling and nurturing the idea of national independence through physical education and sports;

strengthening health, training, improving the function of the growing organism, improving vital skills and physical qualities;

involving students and young people in regular sports activities, wide development of special sports in general education schools, vocational colleges and academic lyceums and neighborhoods;

to arouse interest in sports activities and the achievements of young athletes;

summarizing the development of mass sports and the results of training sessions of the school physical culture team and other physical culture organizations in the country, those who work with children, adolescents, teenagers and girls;

promoting and popularizing sports.

In order for the competition to be successful, they must meet the following pedagogical requirements:

completion of the training process;

access to the sports school (section) event plan;

held according to the specified program;

inform the participants about the competition in advance.

Competitions in all types of sports will be held according to a single rule, training activities of the sports school will be based on the program and mandatory for all participants. Qualified referees and medical personnel serve the competition.

The competition program and loading criteria are developed in accordance with the age and training of the athletes. The document defining the competitions of young athletes is "Standards of competition loadings for children and youth athletes in sports and conditions for holding the competition". The program of the competition and the level of complexity are defined in the loading norm, their quantity, nature, scope, the period of preparation for them and the duration of the recovery period are important.

The duration of training children to participate in the competition at the initial stage of sports training (the first age group) should be at least one year. In the event of a break in sports

training, it is necessary to plan at least 10-15 training sessions in each age group to restore the sports form. Strict regular medical supervision should be carried out during the period of carrying out the loading of children.

For example, we will look at the methodical recommendation on holding a wrestling competition. Specific age groups have their own periods of sports competition. 9-10-year-old children enter internal school competitions, 11-12-year-olds - district and city competitions, 13-14-year-olds - regional level competitions. 15-16-year-old boys and girls are allowed to participate in national competitions. It is important to determine the optimal amount of competition for young athletes. In such sports, it is recommended to have frequent competitions where participation in the competition does not last long and after which the young athletes can quickly recover their strength. It is advisable to hold less sports competitions that require long-term stress and endurance.

Young athletes should regularly participate in general physical training and multi-sport competitions. Such competitions are held in classes, physical culture teams, as well as in the district or in the place where the school is located. The number of competitions depends on the individual characteristics of young athletes. It is necessary for a young athlete to participate less in competitions during the period of insufficient technical preparation, long-term recovery of the body, increased nervousness. And on the contrary, during excellent technical preparation, quick recovery, smoothness of the nervous system, a young athlete can participate in the competition more often. During the preparatory period, young athletes will certainly take part in test competitions of educational importance, because this does not require special training.

During the preparation period, exercises are included in the competition program to improve the general and special preparation of young athletes. During the competition period, competitive exercises, control competitions, comparisons and targeted training sessions with a large load play an important role in order to increase the level of students' engagement.

In the second stage of the competition period, heavy loads should not be given during training. It is necessary to gradually decrease the amount of loading, and increase the intensity of training. Participation of young athletes in regular competitions does not require special changes in the planning of training. It is only necessary to reduce the volume of the training load and at the same time increase its intensity in the last week before the competition. In addition, it is recommended to write *chigil* on the eve of 1-2 days of rest. Preparation for a responsible competition should be extremely thorough. At least 3-4 weeks before it, a check-up will be held, as this is when the competition will be held. In order for the young athlete to perform at his best on the day of the competition, a competition cycle is included in the training plan. It is recommended to make a note 24 hours before the competition (recovery, psychological preparation, what to pay attention to before the competition during training). One should not overdo it when writing *Chigil*. Such writing has a positive effect on the growth of the young athlete's work capacity.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar.

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